

Influence of School Based Interventions on Student Athletes' Track Performance in Secondary Schools in Nakuru County, Kenya

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Submitted: 10-10-2019

Abstract

The main purpose of this study was to analyze influence of school based interventions on Student Athletes' Track Performance in Secondary Schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design targeting 3,584 form two and three students in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. A sample of 351 students was drawn using purposive and stratified random sampling. Data was collected through structured self-administered questionnaires. Hypothesis was tested using regression analysis of .05 level of significance. Data was analyzed by the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer package Version 22.0. The findings of this study may enable coaches to come up with appropriate mechanisms that may help athletes manage their stress effectively. Similarly it may help secondary schools in Kenya institute appropriate interventions to help athletes cope with the stress associated with their sporting careers. The study will also help in building on existing literature related to sources of stress, coping strategies and school based interventions among students athlete in secondary schools. The study will also suggest areas of further research that will create ground for researchers interested in the topic, thus contributing to the expansion of knowledge in the field of counseling psychology. The study established that school based interventions positively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study recommends that the Ministry of Education in Conjunction with Department of Sports of the Ministry of Social Services should develop Secondary School Sports Policy with Sports Stress Management Guidelines to help manage the emerging sports related stress in Secondary Schools in Kenya. Copies of the policy should be availed in all Secondary Schools in Kenya for use by both Games Masters and Teacher Counsellors ion the Schools.

Key Words: *Athletics related stress, Stress Management, School Based Interventions, Athletics Track Performance.*

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1.0 Introduction

Sports psychologists are in high-demand as professional teams realize the value of having their players mentally healthy. They train the mind just as any sports trainer helps train a specific area of the body (Rumbold, Fletcher, & Daniels, 2012). Stress management interventions are important for facilitating athletes' experiences and performances in a range of sport-related settings stress management interventions are important for facilitating athletes' experiences and performances in a range of sport-related settings stress management interventions are important for facilitating athletes' experiences and performances in a range of sport-related settings stress management interventions are important for facilitating athletes' experiences and performances in a range of sport-related settings stress management interventions are important for facilitating athletes' experiences and performances in a range of sport-related settings stress management interventions are important for facilitating athletes' experiences and performances in a range of sport-related settings.

In Kenya, Sports are important in educational institutions as it supports academic performance. However, it has been viewed in two different perspectives in schools as far as their contribution to school connectedness is concerned. One perceives sports as having positive effect on student academic performance while others view it as a hindrance to academic success and a waste of students' precious time. Therefore, this duality in the perception of the contribution of sports should be corrected through research findings. Besides, it is important to note that sports can assume other functions other than the traditional function of entertainment and leisure. These functions include; supporting academic objectives, boosting students' self-concept, self-efficacy, affective needs, behavioural needs, social needs, discipline, retention rates among others (Ongonga *et al.*, 2010).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Kenya is known for its athletic prowess, however, its performance is getting threatened and athletes seem to be resorting to unconventional ways of dealing with their stress related problems. Since athletic talent is mainly identified and discovered in secondary school students, this study set out to examine and provide information on student track athletes' stress level and how it influences performance. Athletes in public secondary schools experience stress like other elite athletes. The stress is contributed by different factors which if not addressed may affect their track performance. It is not clear whether school based interventions influences students'

athletes on track performance of public secondary school student athletes especially in Nakuru County. This is the research gap that this study was to fill. The hypothesis of the study was stated as Ho₁: There is no statistically significant influence of school based interventions on student track athletes' performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 School Based Interventions and Students Athletics Performance

Recent studies have shown that weight training, or muscle conditioning, is also effective toward improving physical endurance toward stressful events. However, current studies have yet to determine which, aerobic activity or muscle conditioning, is more effective long term (Robert, 2004). Less effective than physical conditioning, relaxation training can be performed anywhere and requires a fraction of the time (Robert, 2004).

At the tertiary stage of prevention, primary and secondary methods have either been implemented inadequately or neglected. As a result, employees can no longer function adequately within the environment. To aid employees, managers may have to recommend employees to a crisis intervention programme. Intervention programmes; drug abuse treatment, take time, are often costly, and do not guarantee the employee will return to full productivity. For these reasons, a proper diagnosis and careful implementation of primary and secondary methods are crucial for the well being of managers and employees.

The effectiveness of a Mental Skills Training (MST) program depends on how it is implemented. Many sports psychologists follow an effective sports psychology framework in order to give the athlete the best chance of succeeding (Holland, 2010). Shaw, (2010) suggests that it is important that thoughtful and considered approaches are used within an applied setting. To help the psychologist produce an effective MST program they must implement four phases. The initial phase is the first phase. Poczwardowski, (2010) discovered that a good consultant- client relationship will help develop and maintain the performance of enhancement interventions. This phase involves the coach meeting the athlete, and addressing the individual needs of the athlete. For example: what part of their performance they struggle with (Poczwardowski, 2011). Furthermore the consultant should aim at applying psychometric tests to find out everything about the athlete and what coping strategies should be administered (Howden, 2007).

The second phase is education. Educating the athlete is just as important as developing a solid rapport. Research by Howden (2007) suggests that the athlete is much more likely to succeed if they know that what they are doing is effective. Therefore the relationship between MST and performance must be known by the athlete; though the psychologist must not confuse the athlete by making them sound clever (Morgan, 2010).

The third phase is acquisition phase. Research suggests this phase determine whether athlete succeeds or fails (Shaw, 2005). This phase focuses on the strategies and techniques for learning and developing psychological skills (Mesagno, 2010). Poczwardowski established that goal setting is an integral part of MST programmes. To ensure the psychologist and the athlete work together; a common ground must be sought. He suggests that the athlete should after each session reflect as this may induce a positive mental state.

Practice is the final stage. Implementing the psychological skills into the athletes training regime and competitive performance occurs in this stage (Poczwardowski, 2011). Furthermore, literature suggests that at this stage the practitioner should recreate a competitive environment (Shaw, 2005). By so doing the athlete will be more prepared to deal with their stress.

Haney (2004) compared a cognitive restructuring intervention with progressive muscle relaxation in women athletes. One measure provided assessment of three adaptive coping behaviors, namely, engaging in active coping actions, planning, and suppressing competing activities. The effectiveness of stress interventions can largely be attributed to significantly positive changes in the experience of stress, psychosomatic stress symptoms, and coping resources. These criteria for intervention success are contained within the fourth level. There was evidence that SRT-EA created significant change in both the short- and mid-term in the intended direction for almost all of the selected outcome measures. These intended outcomes are of low to medium effect size. Due to its broad spectrum and size of intervention effects, the SRT-EA seems at least as effective as other stress-management programmes for EA (Sallen, 2017). The results are similar to those of common primary preventative stress interventions for youth in the general population (Lohaus, 2011; Manz, Junge, Neumer & Margraf, 2001). Meta-analyses show that larger effect sizes can hardly be expected in the area of primary prevention (Hosman & Abu-Saad, 2006). It must be noted that the effects of primary preventative interventions can, in most cases, only be observed with significant delay.

Stress-Resistance Training (SRT) is a standardized educational-psychological group intervention programme to improve personal resistance to chronic stress. SRT seems to be a suitable tool for broad and sustainable facilitation of individual resistance to chronic stress. It can be seen as an alternative to universal life-skills programmes for and a complement to interventions with a focus on acute stress and/or psychological skills in sports. Person-centred interventions like SRT-EA should be embedded in larger, more complex programmes for the facilitation of dual careers and health promotion in elite sports. Sustainable effects on stress resistance need to be supported by programmes that (1) create an organisational-structural coupling of academics and sports, and (2) include parents, teachers, and coaches of SRT (Fletcher, Hanton, & Mellalieu, 2006; Lohaus, 2011). Fostering protective factors; optimism, elite young athletes may, therefore, reduce stress and burnout, thus minimizing injury risk.

Regarded as a generalized outcome expectancy or sense of confidence that a goal can be attained, optimism is associated with a sense of control and confidence, making optimists more likely to adopt active and proactive coping strategies, while less likely to engage in avoidance coping. Thus, negative consequences; poor health, poor performance, and injury risk are abated. Studies among elite-level male and female wrestlers have shown a significantly inverse relationship between optimism and both stress and burnout, with optimistic athletes displaying lower levels of emotional/physical exhaustion and sport devaluation, and less of a reduced sense of accomplishment (Gustafsson & Skoog, 2012)

Hardiness represents a trait-like characteristic that influences the manner in which individuals perceive and react to stressful circumstances. Research among adult athletes has shown that hardy individuals are more effective in coping with stress, thus offering protection against stress-induced health issues (Nicolas, Gaudreau & Franche, 2011). Hardiness similarly reflects a state of mental toughness, in that it encapsulates control, commitment, and challenge. Utilized in an athletic setting, such concepts allow athletes to make appropriate decisions about how to cope with stressful situations. Mentally tough individuals are characterized by a strong tendency to view their personal environment as controllable, to perceive themselves as capable and influential, to stay committed even under adverse circumstances, and to consider problems as natural challenges (Gerber, Kalak & Lmola, 2013).

According to Lee (2010) counseling aims at changing the perception of stress allowing an individual to cope with situations that were previously triggering problems. Counseling helps one to evaluate threats and then provide resources to deal with them. Being able to control the environment around is a major part in developing self-confidence which enables an individual to face the challenges ahead. Counseling can help in managing stress and get on with life. Counselors have to deal with stress on a personal level. When discussing stress and how it affects people, counselor will talk about the relationship between the causes of the stress, and the effect of stress. The causes of stress are known as stimulus and the effects are the response. Identifying the cause and effect of stress is a key to stress management and the first step into building a coping mechanism. There is no study that has evaluated influence of counseling as stress intervention among student athletes in secondary schools in Kenya which is the literature gap in the current study.

Relaxation techniques are a great way to help with stress management. Relaxation is not just about peace of mind or enjoying a hobby but it is a process that decreases the effects of stress on your mind and body. Relaxation techniques can help you cope with everyday stress and with stress related to various health problems, such as cancer and pain (Mayo Clinic, 2016). Relaxation techniques can reduce stress symptoms and help an individual enjoy a better quality of life especially if one has an illness. Practicing relaxation techniques can reduce stress symptoms by slowing the heart rate, lowering blood pressure, slowing breathing rate, reducing activity of stress hormones, increasing blood flow to major muscles, reducing muscles tension and chronic pain, improving concentration and mind, lowering fatigue, reducing anger and frustration and boosting confidence to handle problems. There is no study that has assessed influence of relaxation as stress intervention among student athletes in secondary schools in Kenya which is the literature gap in the current study.

2.2 Knowledge Gap

The researcher carried out review of various literatures related to; concept of stress among athletes, athletes' performance in relation to institutional stress and athletes' performance. The critically review showed that there is still need of research to be done on influence of school

based interventions on Student Athletes' Track Performance creating a research gap that the current study analyzed influence of school based interventions on Student Athletes' Track Performance in Secondary Schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

2.3 Theoretical Review

The theoretical aspect of this study is informed by Cognitive Activation Theory of stress (CATS) by Lazarus & Folkman (1984). This theoretical perspective defines stress as a relationship between individuals and their environments. First, stress and coping are viewed as manifestations of dynamic and evaluative interplays between individuals and their environments. Secondly, the cognitive theory of stress and coping suggests that stress and coping are bidirectional processes in that individuals are both agents and objects of environmental change. The theory relies on an assumption that individuals engage in a cognitive appraisal of the environmental condition leading to an evaluation of perceived threats. The cognitive processes include coping mechanisms, an attempt to moderate the environment or an internal attempt to regulate the emotional distress caused by the stressor.

The theory further suggests that repeated experiences with a stimulus allow individuals to adapt and regulate themselves (Ursin & Eriksen, 2004). According to the theory experience may produce discomfort for the individual, arousal and stress is vital to the operation of complex brains. The purpose of arousal is to compel the individual to remove the source of the stress "alarm" and the alarm itself, similar to how it has been argued that the function of effect is to direct action (Frijda, 1996). Or, if not removed, the individual then is able to sustain the activation necessary to handle the stressor. Consequently, the stress experience is part of an adaptive and beneficial system that has survived the test of evolution. CATS theory argues that because the stress alarm occurs when there is a discrepancy between what is desired and what is reality, individuals will associate a probability with the likelihood of abolishing the alarm and its source (Ursin, 2005). This expectancy has a strong influence on the level of arousal. At its simplest, if the person has control and expects a desired outcome, then the alarm may not be activated (i.e., stressors may not be felt, psychologically or physiologically). However, if the future is unpredictable and/or an individual does not have the necessary resources to handle the demands, then the alarm is activated. Further, there are instances when individuals do not

possess the necessary resources to handle the situation and dissociating themselves from it thus engaging a passive response that provokes a positive outcome expectation, reducing stress activation.

To account for individual differences in the activation of the stress response, Lazarus (1966) identified six key decisional components within appraisal and the development of stress, three primary components and three secondary components. Primary appraisal of an event involves addressing what is happening and whether the event is worthy of one's attention (Lazarus, 1993). The individual determines whether the potential stressor is a threat based on previous experiences, knowledge about oneself, and knowledge about the event. Primary appraisal includes three components that are related to the motivational aspects of the encounter with the event. Specifically, primary appraisal includes addressing goal relevance, goal congruence, and the type of ego involvement. Goal relevance indicates whether there is anything at stake to be interfered with by the perceived threat or barrier. If there is nothing to be lost by the presentation of the threat, then no stress response will occur. If the situation is viewed as relevant to the individual's achievement goals, a stress response will result.

The study will also be informed by Rational-Emotive-Behaviour-Theory (REBT) is one of the cognitive behavioural approaches which was founded in 1955 by an American clinical psychologist, Albert Ellis (Scott, 1995). He was the first to pinpoint that people suffer from stress and other conflicts because they believe things which are false. Ellis maintained that emotional and behavioural disturbance was primarily caused by rigid and absolutistic beliefs in the form of musts, shoulds, have to's, got to's (Melgosa, 2000) - demands we make on ourselves, others, the world. In other words, it is individuals who largely upset themselves rather than events, circumstances or other people. In order to minimize emotional disturbance and produce more goal orientated behaviour, rigid or irrational beliefs are pinpointed, challenged and changed to a rational belief system, according to Ellis, 1972.

The stress management strategies would mainly be devoted to cathartic techniques, relaxation, exercise, healthy eating, positive thinking and 'cooling off periods. These are the suggested strategies towards managing stress in my literature review section. From the REBT perspective,

these are essentially short term and palliative methods; unless demandingness is disputed and changed to rational ideas through teaching individuals the ABC model, it is unlikely that stress levels will fall.

When examining the experience of chronic stress for athletes, individual differences become apparent. Stress values mostly fall on the moderate side, yet athletes are significantly more stressed on average than people from the general population; whereas athletes with alarmingly high indicators of stress are mainly elite student athletes (shortly EA) who pursue a school or university career in addition to their elite-level sport (Richartz & Sallen, 2017). Chronic stress seems to play an important role in the dropout of athletic careers (Baron-Thiene & Alfermann, 2015). Exhaustion, depression, and burnout are some of the symptoms often mentioned in connection with chronic stress (Gustafsson, Madigan, & Lundkvist, 2017).

2.4 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Influence of Competition Related Stress on Student Athletes' Track Performance

Figure 1 indicates the relationship between independent and dependent variables. The independent variable was school based interventions. The dependent variable was students tack performance. The model as conceptualized in this study emphasizes on how the independent variables may influence the dependent variables. The study hypothesizes that unmanaged school based stressors is disastrous to athletics by influence their tack performance.

3.0 Research Design

This study undertook an exploratory survey approach with ex-post facto design. *Ex post facto* research, by its very design, investigates the world as it naturally occurs and explores phenomena that have already occurred (Johnson & Christensen, 2008). The study targeted 3,584 form two and three students in schools with high performance in athletics.

Given the sample size of 351 as per Krejcie & Morgan (1970) sampling table, the following formula was used to calculate stratified sample;

$$ss = \frac{z_p}{t_p} Xs$$

Where ss – stratified sample, zp –zonal population, tp – target population and s – sample. The sample size distribution for the study is shown in Table 2. The study purposively picked 5 athlete coaches and 5 Teacher Counselors as key informants to give deeper insight into selected stress factors influencing track performance of Student Athletes. The researcher took half of the sample size to represent both the gender in order to analyze how the different gender responds to stress.

Table 1 Sample Size of Student Athletes in School in Nakuru County

Zone	No. Schools	Total No. of Form		Male	Female
		2 and 3 Students	Sample Size	Athletes	Athletes
A	4	430	42	21	21
B	6	620	61	30	30
C	3	664	65	33	32
D	4	820	80	40	40
E	7	1050	103	52	51
Total	24	3584	351	176	175

The study used a structured questionnaire to collect primary data. Descriptive (frequencies and percentages) analysis and inferential statistics such as chi-square test and Pearson’s correlation analyses were used to analyze data after appropriate data coding. Descriptive statistics were used to investigate or explore one variable at a time. To test the hypotheses, chi-square test and Pearson’s correlation analyses were conducted for each hypothesis and the results interpreted

leading to the rejection or acceptance of the null hypotheses stated earlier. All hypotheses was tested at $\alpha=.05$.

4.0 Findings and Discussions

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 : Distribution of Responses on School Based Interventions to Manage Stress among Athletes

Interventions to manage athletes stress	1	2	3	4	5
The school has assigned sports counsellor to counsel athletes	54(15.9%)	78(22.9%)	46(13.5%)	90(26.5%)	72(21.2%)
The school counselling department has developed stress recovery room for athletes.	82(24.1%)	70(20.6%)	56(16.5%)	60(17.6%)	72(21.2%)
The counselling department has developed support groups to help athletes recover from stress.	94(27.6%)	60(17.6%)	60(17.6%)	76(22.4%)	50(14.7%)
Teacher Counsellors have developed goal setting therapy to help athletes recover from stress.	78(22.9%)	60(17.6%)	62(18.2%)	80(23.5%)	60(17.6%)
Teacher Counsellors have training sessions on personal conflict management	62(18.2%)	64(18.8%)	58(17.1%)	88(25.9%)	68(20%)
School has referral arrangement for treatment depressions.	88(25.9%)	64(18.8%)	36(10.6%)	68(20%)	84(24.7%)
Teacher Counsellors has drug abstinence therapy for athletes.	78(22.9%)	66(19.4%)	62(18.2%)	64(18.8%)	70(20.6%)
The school has special stress recovery diet for athletes	120(35.3%)	66(19.4%)	38(11.2%)	60(17.6%)	56(16.5%)

From data presented on Table 1, it was also observed that 54(15.9%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'The school has assigned sports counsellor to counsel athletes'* while 78(22.9%) disagreed; 46(13.5%) were undecided; 90(26.5%) agreed and 72(21.2%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: *'The school counselling department has developed stress recovery room for athletes'* it was observed that 82(24.1%) completely disagreed; 70(20.6%) disagreed; 56(16.5%) were undecided; 60(17.6%) agreed and 72(21.2%) completely agreed. Similarly, 94(27.6%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'The counselling department has developed support groups to help athletes recover*

from stress’ while 60(17.6%) disagreed; 60(17.6%) were undecided; 76(22.4%) agreed and 50(14.7%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 78(22.9%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *‘Teacher Counsellors have developed goal setting therapy to help athletes recover from stress’* while 60(17.6%) disagreed; 62(18.2%) were undecided; 80(23.5%) agreed and 60(17.6%) completely agreed with the statement.

With regard to the statement: *‘Teacher Counsellors have training sessions on personal conflict management’* it was observed that 62(18.2%) completely disagreed; 64(18.8%) disagreed; 58(17.1%) were undecided; 88(25.9%) agreed and 68(20%) completely agreed. Similarly, 88(25.9%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *‘School has referral arrangement for treatment on depressions’* while 64(18.8%) disagreed; 36(10.6%) were undecided; 68(20%) agreed and 84(24.7%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 78(22.9%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *‘Teacher Counsellors has drug abstinence therapy for athletes’* while 66(19.4%) disagreed; 62(18.2%) were undecided; 64(18.8%) agreed and 70(20.6%) completely agreed with the statement. With regard to the statement: *‘The school has special stress recovery diet for athletes’* it was observed that 120(35.3%) completely disagreed; 66(19.4%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 60(17.6%) agreed and 56(16.5%) completely agreed.

The level of stress coping strategies was conceptualized as a composite variable derived from the averages of non-missing responses on 8 items. The overall averages were divided into 3 categories: Low; Moderate and High. The expected highest score per respondent was 50, and therefore, transition points were $x \leq 13$ for Low; $x \geq 14 \leq 26$ for Moderate and $x \geq 27$ for high levels of completion related stress. The findings of the study are presented on Table 18

Table 2: Distribution of Interventions to Manage Athletes Stress

Interventions to Manage Athletes Stress	Frequency	Percentage
Low	18	5.3
Moderate	228	67.1
High	94	27.6
Total	340	100.0

Data presented in Table 2 indicates that the modal group of respondents presented moderate institutional related stress levels (67.1%) compared to 5.3% of respondents who presented low levels and 27.6% who presented high levels.

Table 3: Distribution of Responses on Athletes Track Performance

Institutional Stress	1	2	3	4	5
I worry quite a bit about what the teachers think of my performance.	40(11.8%)	112(32.9%)	38(11.2%)	36(10.6%)	114(33.5%)
I tend to do lots of planning about how to reach my goals.	48(14.1%)	76(22.4%)	36(10.6%)	26(7.6%)	154(45.3%)
I feel confident that I will play well.	34(10%)	80(23.5%)	70(20.6%)	38(11.2%)	118(34.7%)
When a coach or manager criticizes me, I become upset rather than feel helped.	78(22.9%)	98(28.8%)	60(17.6%)	46(13.5%)	58(17.1%)
It is easy for me to keep distracting thoughts from interfering with something I am watching or listening to.	68(20%)	82(24.1%)	66(19.4%)	64(18.8%)	60(17.6%)
I put a lot of pressure on myself by worrying about how I will perform.	56(16.5%)	96(28.2%)	36(10.6%)	44(12.9%)	108(31.8%)
I set my own performance goals for each practice.	22(6.5%)	74(21.8%)	64(18.8%)	58(17.1%)	122(35.9%)
I don't have to be pushed to practice or play hard; I give 100%.	50(14.7%)	90(26.5%)	38(11.2%)	44(12.9%)	118(34.7%)
If a coach criticizes or yells at me, I correct the mistake without getting upset about it.	56(16.5%)	72(21.2%)	54(15.9%)	46(13.5%)	112(32.9%)
I handle unexpected situations in my sport very well.	56(16.5%)	90(26.5%)	56(16.5%)	56(16.5%)	82(24.1%)
When things are going badly, I tell myself to keep calm, and this works for me.	58(17.1%)	80(23.5%)	56(16.5%)	48(14.1%)	98(28.8%)
The more pressure there is during a game, the more I enjoy it.	52(15.3%)	98(28.8%)	48(14.1%)	46(13.5%)	96(28.2%)
While competing, I worry about making mistakes or failing to come through.	82(24.1%)	74(21.8%)	54(15.9%)	60(17.6%)	70(20.6%)
I have my own game plan worked out in my head long before the game begins.	72(21.2%)	80(23.5%)	60(17.6%)	40(11.8%)	88(25.9%)

When I feel myself getting too tense, I can quickly relax my body and calm myself.	60(17.6%)	78(22.9%)	56(16.5%)	54(15.9%)	92(27.1%)
To me, pressure situations are challenges that I welcome.	80(23.5%)	94(27.6%)	46(13.5%)	42(12.4%)	78(22.9%)
I think about and imagine what will happen if I fail.	62(18.2%)	82(24.1%)	64(18.8%)	40(11.8%)	92(27.1%)
I maintain emotional control regardless of how things are going for me.	52(15.3%)	66(19.4%)	46(13.5%)	60(17.6%)	116(34.1%)
It is easy for me to direct my attention and focus on a single object or person.	52(15.3%)	72(21.2%)	46(13.5%)	64(18.8%)	106(31.2%)
When I fail to reach my goals, it makes me try even harder.	50(14.7%)	60(17.6%)	44(12.9%)	52(15.3%)	134(39.4%)
I improve my skills by listening carefully to advice and instruction from coaches and managers.	42(12.4%)	56(16.5%)	38(11.2%)	60(17.6%)	144(42.4%)
I make fewer mistakes when the pressure is on because I concentrate better.	54(15.9%)	88(25.9%)	38(11.2%)	66(19.4%)	94(27.6%)

Data presented in Table 2 indicates that 40(11.8%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I worry quite a bit about what the teachers think of my performance'* while 112(32.9%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 36(10.6%) agreed and 114(33.5%) completely agreed with the statement. Similarly, 48(14.1%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I tend to do lots of planning about how to reach my goals'* while 76(22.4%) disagreed; 36(10.6%) were undecided; 26(7.6%) agreed and 154(45.3%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 34(10%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I feel confident that I will play well'* while 80(23.5%) disagreed; 70(20.6%) were undecided; 38(11.2%) agreed and 118(34.7%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: *'When a coach or manager criticizes me, I become upset rather than feel helped'* it was observed that 78(22.9%) completely disagreed; 98(28.8%) disagreed; 60(17.6%) were undecided; 46(13.5%) agreed and 58(17.1%) completely agreed. Similarly, 68(20%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'It is easy for me to keep distracting thoughts from interfering with something I am watching or listening to'* while 82(24.1%)

disagreed; 66(19.4%) were undecided; 64(18.8%) agreed and 60(17.6%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 56(16.5%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I put a lot of pressure on myself by worrying about how I will perform'* while 96(28.2%) disagreed; 36(10.6%) were undecided; 44(12.9%) agreed and 108(31.8%) completely agreed with the statement. With regard to the statement: *'I set my own performance goals for each practice'* it was observed that 22(6.5%) completely disagreed; 74(21.8%) disagreed; 64(18.8%) were undecided; 58(17.1%) agreed and 122(35.9%) completely agreed. It was observed that 50(14.7%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I don't have to be pushed to practice or play hard; I give 100%'* while 90(26.5%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 44(12.9%) agreed and 118(34.7%) completely agreed with the statement.

Similarly, 56(16.5%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'If a coach criticizes or yells at me, I correct the mistake without getting upset about it'* while 72(21.2%) disagreed; 54(15.9%) were undecided; 46(13.5%) agreed and 112(32.9%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 56(16.5%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I handle unexpected situations in my sport very well'* while 90(26.5%) disagreed; 56(16.5%) were undecided; 56(16.5%) agreed and 82(24.1%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: *'When things are going badly, I tell myself to keep calm, and this works for me'* it was observed that 58(17.1%) completely disagreed; 80(23.5%) disagreed; 56(16.5%) were undecided; 48(14.1%) agreed and 98(28.8%) completely agreed. Similarly, 52(15.3%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'The more pressure there is during a game, the more I enjoy it'* while 98(28.8%) disagreed; 48(14.1%) were undecided; 46(13.5%) agreed and 96(28.2%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 82(24.1%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'While competing, I worry about making mistakes or failing to come through'* while 74(21.8%) disagreed; 54(15.9%) were undecided; 60(17.6%) agreed and 70(20.6%) completely agreed with the statement. With regard to the statement: *'I have my own game plan worked out in my head long before the game begins'* it was observed that 72(21.2%) completely disagreed; 80(23.5%) disagreed; 60(17.6%) were undecided; 40(11.8%) agreed and 88(25.9%) completely agreed. Similarly, 60(17.6%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'When I feel myself getting too tense, I can quickly relax my body and calm myself'* while 78(22.9%) disagreed; 56(16.5%) were undecided; 54(15.9%) agreed and 92(27.1%) completely agreed with the

statement. It was also observed that 80(23.5%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'To me, pressure situations are challenges that I welcome'* while 94(27.6%) disagreed; 46(13.5%) were undecided; 42(12.4%) agreed and 78(22.9%) completely agreed with the statement. With regard to the statement: *'I think about and imagine what will happen if I fail'* it was observed that 62(18.2%) completely disagreed; 82(24.1%) disagreed; 64(18.8%) were undecided; 40(11.8%) agreed and 92(27.1%) completely agreed. It was observed that 52(15.3%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I maintain emotional control regardless of how things are going for me'* while 66(19.4%) disagreed; 46(13.5%) were undecided; 60(17.6%) agreed and 116(34.1%) completely agreed with the statement.

Similarly, 52(15.3%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'It is easy for me to direct my attention and focus on a single object or person'* while 72(21.2%) disagreed; 46(13.5%) were undecided; 64(18.8%) agreed and 106(31.2%) completely agreed with the statement. It was also observed that 50(14.7%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'When I fail to reach my goals, it makes me try even harder'* while 60(17.6%) disagreed; 44(12.9%) were undecided; 52(15.3%) agreed and 134(39.4%) completely agreed with the statement. Concerning the statement: *'I improve my skills by listening carefully to advice and instruction from coaches and managers'* it was observed that 42(12.4%) completely disagreed; 56(16.5%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 60(17.6%) agreed and 144(42.4%) completely agreed. Similarly, 54(15.9%) of respondents completely disagreed with the statement *'I make fewer mistakes when the pressure is on because I concentrate better'* while 88(25.9%) disagreed; 38(11.2%) were undecided; 66(19.4%) agreed and 94(27.6%) completely agreed with the statement.

The level of institutional related stress was conceptualized as a composite variable derived from the averages of non-missing responses on 22 items. The overall averages were divided into 3 categories: Low; Moderate and High. The expected highest score per respondent was 50, and therefore, transition points were $x \leq 37$ for Low; $x \geq 38 \leq 74$ for Moderate and $x \geq 75$ for high levels of completion related stress. The findings of the study are presented on Table 3

4.2 Inferential Statistics on the Relationship between School Based Interventions and Athletes' Track Performance

The main objective in the study was to examine whether school based interventions used by students' athletes has any influence on track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. To achieve this objective the following hypothesis was formulated;

H₀: There is no statistically significant influence of school based interventions used by students' athletes on student athletes' track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

The hypothesis postulated that school based interventions has no significant influence on students' athletes' track performance. To ascertain the truth in the assumption simple regression analysis of school based interventions on student athletes track performance was done. The results are presented in tables 4, 5 and 6.

Table 4 indicates that the Pearson Correlation coefficient between school based interventions and students athletes track performance was statistically significant, ($r=0.144$, $p=0.000$). The r-square was found to be .021. This indicates that only 2.1% of the variance in student athletes track performance can be explained by school based interventions. Therefore 97.9% of the variance in student athletes track performance was explained by other factors outside this study.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	r	r Square	Adjusted r Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Sig.
1	.144 ^a	.021	.018	5.040	0.008

Table 5 shows the results of simple regression analysis of influence of school based interventions on student athletes' track performance.

Table 5: Simple Regression Analysis of the influence of school based interventions on student athletes' track performance

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	181.757	1	181.757	7.156	.008 ^b
Residual	8584.655	338	25.398		
Total	8766.412	339			

From Table 5 it can be seen that the F value was significant ($F(1,338) = 7.156, p = .008$). This implies that there is a significant influence of school based interventions on the student athletes' track performance. School based interventions could be used to predict student athletes' track performance in secondary schools. The null hypothesis (H_0) that there is no statistically significant influence of school based interventions on student athletes' track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya, Kenya as rejected at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that school based interventions can be used as a predictor of student athletes' track performance in secondary schools.

Table 34 presents regression coefficients between personality related stress and student athletes' track performance.

Table 6: Regression Coefficients of the Influence of School Based Interventions on Student Athletes' Track Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	19.248	1.182		16.289	.000
Interventions to manage athletes stress	1.383	.517	.144	2.675	.008

The results shown in Table 6 indicated that the beta value was significant ($\beta = 1.383, p = 0.008$). The simple regression model therefore can be used to predict student athletes' track performance from institutional related stress is given by

$$Y = 19.248 + 1.383X_3 + \varepsilon \text{ where}$$

Y = student athletes track performance

X₃ = school based interventions

The finding in this study is similar to Hamilton (2007) who argues that types of self-talk aid the athlete regardless of how they are delivered and that “the nature, content and delivery of self-talk may not be as important as individual interpretation of that self-talk.” (p.237). It is important that care and consideration is present when the psychologist implements negative self-talk (Hamilton, 2007). In relation to sport, psychologists must focus on examining self-talks effectiveness on discrete skills and performance processes rather than on the competitive outcome or global performance (Shaw, 2005). An athlete who is in the early skill acquisition phase will benefit from an assisted positive self-talk intervention as they will “stay motivated for longer, acquire the skill more rapidly and bring about performance increases earlier.” (Hamilton, 2007). To conclude, it is more beneficial to the athlete if the psychologist uses positive self-talk rather than negative self-talk. The latter should only be used once the athlete’s performances have improved (Plaatjie, 2011).

The established relationship between school interventions and student athletes’ performance is supported by Peluso, Ross, Gfeller and Lavoie (2005) who agree that imagery along with self-talk will increase positive athletic performance. To further understand the benefits of self-talk and imagery, Peluso et al. studied what is the optimal time frame between self-talk and a golf-putting activity in collegiate students. Golf is viewed to be a more mentally demanding sport, while, for example, football is viewed as a more physically demanding sport. Thus, the mental aspect of golf is tremendously important to the outcome of the athletic performance and, as such, must be understood as much as the physical demands of the sport. On this scale, swimming and track and field also tend to be viewed as a more mentally demanding sports for the athletes are required to focus on technique rather than pure physical strength.

5.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

5.3. Conclusions

The study examined whether school based interventions used by students’ athletes has any influence on track performance in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study

established that school based interventions used by students' athletes positively influences track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were made:

Guidance and counselling departments should design appropriate programmes for school based interventions promote athletes self image to increase the positive influence on track performance among athletes in secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya.

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